

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART VI,
INTERACTION OF NITROSYL CHLORIDE ON SUBSTITUTED
AMIDES OF ACETOACETIC ACID

BY K. G. NAIK, R. K. TRIVEDI AND B. N. MANKAD

In order to study the reactivity of the methylene group $-CH_2-$ in the case of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid, the interaction of nitrosyl chloride with the following substances has been investigated: (i) acetoacetanilide, (ii) acetoacet-*o*-tolylamide, (iii) acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide (iv) acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide (v) acetoacet- α -naphthylamide, (vi) acetoacet- β -naphthylamide.

All the above compounds react with nitrosyl chloride yielding their respective yellow *is*nitroso derivatives (oximes) without giving the corresponding isomers.

The present work was undertaken in the expectation of throwing some light on the relationship between the chemical activity exhibited by and the absorption in the ultraviolet of (1) the various substituted amides of acetoacetic acid, (2) their chloro derivatives and (3) their *is*nitroso derivatives, which can respectively be generally represented as :

where R = phenyl, tolyl, xylyl or naphthyl group.

It was proposed to investigate the difference in the absorption in the ultraviolet and the general chemical activity of the amides by transforming the reactive methylene group contained in the compound into $-CHCl-$ and $-C=NOH$ groups, and to publish the results in a series of communications. For this purpose, the following studies have been made :

1. Interaction of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid with sulphuryl chloride giving monochloro derivatives of the amides.
2. Interaction of the above amides with nitrosyl chloride giving *is*nitroso derivatives of the amides.
3. The absorption in the ultraviolet of the amides of acetoacetic acid and of their monochloro and *is*nitroso derivatives.
4. Velocity of hydrolysis of the amides in alkaline and acidic media.
5. Velocity of replacement of chlorine from the $-CHCl-$ group.

The following substances have been selected for the purpose :

* (1) Acetoacetanilide. * (2) Acetoacet-*o*-tolylamide. * (3) Acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide. * (4) Acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide. * (5) Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide. * (6) Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide. * (7) Monochloro-acetoacetanilide. (8) Monochloro-acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide. (9) Monochloro acetoacet- α -naphthylamide. * (10) *is*Nitrosoacetoacetanilide. (11) *is*Nitroso-acetoacet-*o*-tolylamide. (12) *is*Nitroso-acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide. (13) *is*Nitroso-acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide. (14) *is*Nitroso-acetoacet- α -naphthylamide. (15) *is*Nitroso-acetoacet- β -naphthylamide.

The substances marked (*) in the above list are known. The remaining have been prepared for the first time.

Naik and his collaborators have studied the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms in the case of organic compounds, containing the grouping $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CO}-$ with different agents, e.g. sulphur monochloride, sulphur dichloride, sulphuryl chloride, selenium tetrachloride, thionyl chloride, mercury acetamide, mercury acetate, mercury acetamide, mercury acetate and sulphur dichloride (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379, 1231, 2592; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 525; 1926, 8, 260; 1927, 4, 11; 1928, 8, 579; 1930, 7, 611; 1930, 7, 655; 1930, 7, 137; 1932, 9, 127; 1931, 8, 29; 1932, 9, 855; 1932, 9, 185; 1936, 13, 25).

However no study of the interaction between the substances of the above mentioned type and nitrosyl chloride has been made. This investigation was, therefore, undertaken to elucidate the reactivity of the methylene group situated between the carbonyl groups and the mode of reactions in the case of substituted amides of acetoacetic acid. It is likely that

(1) Nitrosyl chloride may act as a chlorinating agent. In this case it would be expected to give either monochloro or dichloro compounds, where the hydrogen atoms of the reactive methylene group may be replaced by chlorine. That nitrosyl chloride does behave as a chlorinating agent is evident from the researches carried out by several investigators (Solanina, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 30, 437; Tilden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 489; Titherley, *ibid.*, 1894, 66, 521).

(2) Nitrosyl chloride may act as a 'nitrosating agent' giving rise to nitroso or isonitroso compounds. This mode of reaction has been amply studied by several workers (Tilden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 489; Whiteley, *ibid.*, 1900, 77, 1040; 1903, 83, 24; Tsker and Jones, *ibid.*, 1909, 38, 1910).

(3) It is also possible that nitrosyl chloride may form additive products with unsaturated compounds (*cf.* Tilden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 554; Tonnie, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 169; 1887, 20, 2987; Tilden and Sudborough, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 479; Wallach, *Annalen*, 1888, 248, 245; 1889, 282, 109; 1889, 283, 251; 1892, 270, 174; 1893, 277, 153; 1904, 332, 395; 1905, 336, 12).

Taking into consideration the varied probabilities of the reactions, it was thought interesting to study comprehensively the mode of the reactions, in the case of substituted amides of acetoacetic acid. For that purpose, substances from 1 to 6 have been made to react with nitrosyl chloride. The substances are dissolved in anhydrous benzene and gaseous nitrosyl chloride, prepared by Tilden's method (*loc. cit.*), is passed into the solution until saturation, the flask being surrounded by ice-cold water. It is subsequently refluxed over a water-bath till the solvent is free from gaseous substances and is then allowed to evaporate spontaneously. The product is washed thoroughly with light petroleum and repeatedly crystallised from suitable solvents such as chloroform, light petroleum etc.

That the substances, have the structure :

is evident from the following :

The qualitative and the quantitative analysis of the products show the total absence of chlorine proving that the substance formed is neither a monochloro nor an additive product of the amide with the nitrosyl chloride.

(2) The substances form characteristic violet ferrous salts and yellow alkali salts showing the presence of $=\text{NOH}$ group (Whiteley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 24). Further, Victor Meyer (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 2076) and other workers studied the interaction of nitrous acid on acetoacetic

acid. The product obtained by this interaction is the same as that obtained by Whiteley by the interaction of nitrosyl chloride with ethyl acetoacetate. Knorr (*Annalen*, 1884, 238, 80) studied the interaction of nitrous acid on acetoacetanilide. He also obtained the *isonitroso* derivatives of the amide to which he attributed a similar constitution as given by Whiteley.

(3) From the constitution of the original compounds, it appears that the acidic hydrogen in =NOH is furnished by the swinging of the hydrogen atom which formed a part of the group.

(4) The formation of yellow alkali salts is characteristic of α -oximino-ketones to which the oximes under discussion belong.

From the foregoing, it becomes evident that the reaction of nitrosyl chloride on the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid takes place according to the second possibility.

Compounds 11 to 15 were obtained in the above way from compounds 2 to 6, the *isonitroso* derivatives of acetoacetanilide (1) being already known.

It was expected that substituted amides of acetoacetic acid would give either (1) structural isomers or (2) stereoisomers in the case of their oximes as was shown by Whiteley in the case of the oximes of substituted amides of malonic acid (*loc. cit.*). Contrary to our expectations, however, no such isomers could be isolated in spite of many attempts being made to separate them, if in any case present, by using various solvents. Absence of existence of isomers has also been noted in the case of (1) ethyl acetoacetate (Whiteley, *loc. cit.*), (2) acetyl acetone (Zanetti, *Gazetta*, 23, II, 303), (3) acetoacetanilide (Knorr, *loc. cit.*), (4) cyanoacetic ester and cyanoacetamide (Conrad and Schulze, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 735). However, cyanoacetanilide gives two *isonitroso* derivatives.

From the above, one is led to infer that:—

(1) The effect of aliphatic groups on the formation of isomerides appears to be negative. As stated above, in acetyl acetone, acetoacetic ester, cyanoacetic ester, cyanoacetamide, acetoacetanilide etc., the effect of groups such as CH_2CO -, $-\text{OOC}_2\text{H}_5$ -, $-\text{CONH}_2$ -, is predominantly negative. This is especially so when the groups are asymmetrically situated with respect to carbon to which *isonitroso* group has been attached. In the case of malonamide, however, where the $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups are symmetrically situated with respect to the carbon to which NOH group has been attached, formation of isomers results.

(2) The effect of aromatic groups favours the formation of isomeric oximes, when they are either the only groups in the molecule or they are the predominant groups in the same. In this way the formation of isomerides in the case of cyanoacetanilide can be explained.

(3) When the aromatic groups are balanced by similarly situated aliphatic groups in the same molecule, their effect is counterbalanced by the effect of the latter ones. This fact has been well observed by many workers in this direction. To quote Shriner and others (Gilmann, *Org. Chem.*, Vol. I, p. 390) 'Usually in the aliphatic series only one form can be isolated. Most of the known pairs of isomers have been obtained from aromatic aldehydes and ketones. It can be added to this that whenever a molecule is a combination of aliphatic and aromatic groups, the formation of isomeric substances would depend upon the balance of the influence of those groups, positive results being obtained if the aromatic groups are the only groups or the most predominating groups in the molecules, and negative results being obtained whenever

the aliphatic groups are the only groups by themselves or when they are sufficiently influential enough to counterbalance the influence of the aromatic part in the molecule.

(4) According to Hantzsch (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2164) different groups exhibit different attractions for the hydroxyl group of the oxime and hence under the circumstances only one form is stable. In the present case therefore it is possible to assume that the difference existing between the attractions of the CH_2CO - and $-\text{CONHR}$ groups on the hydroxyl group of the oxime, may be responsible for preventing the formation of the expected stereoisomers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Interaction of Acetoacetanilide with Sulphuryl Chloride.—Acetoacetanilide (5b g.) was suspended in anhydrous ether (360 c.c.) cooled in ice-water. Sulphuryl chloride (39 g.) was added dropwise, the solution being mechanically stirred for a quarter of an hour after the sulphuryl chloride was added, when a white precipitate of monochloro-acetoacetanilide separated out. It was filtered under suction and after being thoroughly washed with ether and dry light petroleum was kept over sodium hydroxide under reduced pressure. Finally it was crystallised from alcohol. The other compounds were prepared and purified in a similar way. The properties and analysis of the compounds have been given in Table I.

TABLE I

Name of the compound.	M.p.	Crystalline structure.	Solubility	Analysis	
				Found.	Calc.
Monochloro-acetoacetanilide	138°	Needles from alcohol	Highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, sparingly soluble in alcohol and practically insoluble in ether and light petroleum	Cl, 17.05	16.7
Monochloro-acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.	114°	Plates from 50% alcohol	Do	14.75	14.81
Monochloro-acetoacet- <i>n</i> -sophthylamide	135°	Needles from alcohol	Do	13.36	13.38

Interaction of Acetoacetanilide with Nitrosyl Chloride.—Acetoacetanilide (10 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 c.c.), and the mixture was surrounded by ice-water. Dry nitrosyl chloride gas was passed slowly, shaking the whole reaction mixture all the time till the mixture was saturated with nitrosyl chloride. The solution gradually attained yellow colour which tended to deepen and finally assumed a deep reddish yellow colour. It was subsequently refluxed on a water-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas and the excess of nitrosyl chloride ceased. Spontaneous evaporation of the solution left behind a solid yellow mass which was crystallised from a mixture of five parts of light petroleum and one part of chloroform. The other compounds were prepared and purified in a similar way. The analysis and properties of the compounds have been given in Table II.

TABLE II

Name of compound.	M.p.	Crystalline structure.	Solubility.	Analysis.	
				Found:	Calc.
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet-anilide.	100°	Short prismatic needles. Pale yellow	Soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride; sparingly in ether; insoluble in light petroleum.	N, 13'97	13'59
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet- <i>p</i> -tolylamide.	92°	Long orange yellow needles	Do except that it is soluble in petroleum.	12'57	12'73
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -tolylamide.	130°	Long yellow silky needles	"	11'71	12'73
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet-1:3:4-xylyl-amide.	145°	Very fine light yellow short needles	"	11'98	11'97
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet- α -naphthyl-amide.	138°	Deep yellow tiny needles	"	10'82	10'94
<i>iso</i> Nitroso-acetoacet- β -naphthyl-amide.	152°	Tiny light silky yellow needles	"	10'5	10'94

The authors are grateful to H. H. the Maharaja Gaekwad's Government for necessary facilities given for carrying out the above work.

S. J. SCIENCE INSTITUTE,
BARODA.

Received July 28, 1953.